

J-V CHARACTERISTICS OF GAN BASED SOLAR CELL WITH INGAN-QUANTUM-DOTS LAYERS IN THE ABSORBER

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Abstract:

Because of efficient energy harvesting capability from the low-energy photons of the solar spectra, quantum dot (QD) based thin film solar cells draw immense attention in the recent years. Of various structures proposed in the literature, multi-stacked InGaN QD structures are very much favorable for the photovoltaic applications. InGaN (0.7-3.4eV) can cover almost the full range of the solar spectra (0.5-3.5 eV), has higher carrier mobility and saturation velocity as well as has higher absorption coefficients. These stacked InGaN QDs are inserted in the i-region of GaN p-i-n solar cells and depending on the dot density, they can act as the generation-recombination centers. A few models are found in the literature that described the light absorption, the carrier generation and generation in the QDs and the transport of photo-generated carriers. However, the comprehensive models for the J-V characteristics of these QD cells have not been developed yet. This work aims to develop a model that can accurately determine the J-V characteristics of GaN/InGaN based quantum dot solar cells.

Keywords: Multi-stacked dot layers, photovoltaic cell, generation-recombination centers, absorption coefficients, photo-generated carriers.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a quantum dot solar cell the quantum dots are used as an absorbing photovoltaic material inside the intrinsic layer. Quantum dots have adjustable band gap. The band gap can be changed by changing the dot size. This feature allows quantum dots to absorb different parts of the solar spectrum. As quantum dots are nano-particles, using them does not increase the size of the solar cell. According to Shockley–Queisser limit the efficiency cannot exceed 33.7% [1]; but with quantum dot the theoretical efficiency is up to 65% [2]. So far the highest recorded efficiency for a quantum dot solar cell is 9% [3], which is roughly half the performance of commercial bulk silicon cell. But this new field has a huge potential. With new researches this technology can begin a new era for solar cell.

Various materials can be used as quantum dot material, like-CdSe, InAs or InGaN. In CdSe/TiO₂ based solar cell CdSe is used as quantum dot [4]. CdSe has a carrier

mobility of 660 cm²/Vs [5]. In InAs/GaAs based Quantum dot solar cell InAs is used as quantum dot material [6]. InAs has a carrier mobility of 250 cm²/Vs [7]. For InGaN the carrier mobility is 820 cm²/Vs [8]. InGaN has a bandgap range of (0.7-3.4) eV [9] which covers full range of solar spectrum. So InGaN is a better choice as a Quantum Dot material then the other alternatives.

If the surface recombination rate of a solar cell of multilayer quantum dot stacks structure is observed, a particular layer of quantum dot stack can act as a generation center or a recombination center [10]. This phenomenon depends on various parameters, like- electric field (E), capture time (τ_c), density of free electron etc. For generation of high power the quantum dot stacks are expected to work as a generation center. Previous studies show the effects of various parameters on the performance of a solar cell [10][11]. But, all these works did not show the effect of series resistance (R_s) and the effect of load voltage (V_L) on the current-voltage (J-V) characteristics of these QD solar cells. This work, therefore, aims to show the effect of the R_s and V_L variation on the J-V characteristics. Based on the concept of the perturbation theory, an analytical model for the J-V characteristics has been developed which includes the effect of R_s as well as V_L variation. The effect of various parameters like- surface dot density (N_s), width of absorber layer (W_i) and bandgap of dot material (E_{gd}) has been observed in this work, which has not been observed before.

II. ANALYSIS

The energy band diagram of quantum dot solar cell is shown in Fig 1, where quantum dots are inserted inside the intrinsic layer [12]. Based on this diagram the surface recombination rate can be determined as follows:

Four distinct processes of absorption of photon, release and recombination of carrier can be observed in each of the layers of QD stack. The processes are- (a) Capture of electron by QDs from barrier region, (b) Release of electron, (c) Recombination in QD (d) Generation of QD [10].

Above four processes we have four different equations:

1. $R_1^k = \alpha n(z_k) N_s (1 - f_n^k)$
2. $R_2^k = \beta N_s f_n^k$
3. $R_3^k = \gamma N_s (f_n^k - f_{n0})$
4. $R_4^k = \eta N_s (1 - f_n^k)$

Fig 1 Energy band diagram of quantum dot solar cell

Where α is Capture coefficient, β is Release Coefficient, γ is Recombination Coefficient and η is Generation Coefficient. f_n^k is non-equilibrium population of QDs in the k^{th} layer. In steady state condition-
 $(R_1^k - R_2^k) + (R_4^k - R_3^k) = 0$ (1)
 In dark condition $R_3^k = R_4^k = 0$. Considering this condition the electron density and QDs population probability becomes

$$n_0 = N_c e^{\frac{E_F - E_C}{kT}}, f_{n0} = \left[1 + e^{\frac{E_F - E_C}{kT}} \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Therefore the coefficient α can be written as, $\beta = n_1 \alpha$

$$\text{where, } n_1 = N_c e^{\left[\frac{E_C - E_N}{kT} \right]} \quad (3)$$

Now using β in equation (1) and solving with respect to population factor f_n^k we have

$$f_n^k = \frac{\alpha n(z_k) + \gamma f_{n0} + \eta}{\alpha (n(z_k) + n_1) + \gamma + \eta} \quad (4)$$

So surface recombination rate for k^{th} layer

$$U_s^k = R_1^k - R_2^k \quad (5)$$

Finally from equation (4) we have

$$U_s^k = \left[n(z_k) - \frac{(n(z_k) + n_1)(\alpha n(z_k) + \gamma f_{n0} + \eta)}{\alpha (n(z_k) + n_1) + \gamma + \eta} \right] N_s \alpha$$

where, $\alpha_c = 1/N_D \tau_c$, $\gamma = 1/\tau_r$, $\eta = 1/\tau_{opt}$

Finally surface recombination rates becomes- [3]

$$U_k^s = \frac{N_s}{N_D \tau_c} \left[n(z_k) - \frac{\{n(z_k) + n_1\} \left\{ \frac{n(z_k)}{\tau_c N_D} + \frac{f_{n0}}{\tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_{opt}} \right\}}{\frac{n(z_k) + n_1}{N_D \tau_c} + \frac{1}{\tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_{opt}}} \right] \quad (6)$$

where U_k^s is Surface recombination rate, N_s is Surface dot density, N_D is doping density, τ_c is capture time, $n(z_k)$ is density of electron at the frontal surface of k^{th} layer, n_1 is Equilibrium Electron Concentration in

Confined Energy, f_{n0} is equilibrium Fermi-Dirac occupation probability, τ_r is life time of carrier and τ_{opt} is optical generation time. Positive value of U_k^s refers that the quantum dot stack is working as a recombination center and negative value refers to generation center. It is expected that the layers of quantum dot stack will work as a generation center. If n_1 is higher than n_z^k then the layer of QD stack will work as a generation center. Otherwise they will work as a recombination center.

Equation (6) suggests that with the increase of Surface Dot Density (N_s) the generation rate will increase. And as the generation rate increases the photo-generated current density will increase. Considering the load voltage (V_L) and series resistance (R_s) the equation of electric field is

$$E = \frac{V_{bi} - (V_L + I R_s)}{W_i} \quad (7)$$

Photo Generated Current Derivation

There is no electric field in the emitter region. So the basic solar cell equations become

$$J_n = q D_n \frac{dn(x)}{dx} \quad (8)$$

As Recombination rate is negligible

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q(-G_n) \quad (9)$$

Now considering equation (8) and (9)

$$\frac{d^2 n(x)}{dx^2} - \frac{n(x)}{L_n^2} = -\frac{\alpha G_0}{D_n} e^{-\alpha x} \quad (10)$$

$n(x)$ will be obtained by solving equation (10). Using equation (8) the electron current can be obtained.

J_n

$$= -q V_{0n} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} + \alpha L_n \right) - e^{-\alpha x} \left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \cosh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) + \sinh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) \right)}{\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \sinh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) + \cosh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right)} \right. \\ \left. - \alpha L_n e^{-\alpha W_e} \right] + \frac{q D_n}{L_n} \times \frac{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \cosh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) + \sinh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) \right)}{\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \sinh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right) + \cosh \left(\frac{W_e}{L_n} \right)} \\ \times n_{e0}$$

Using the similar method the hole current for base region can be obtained.

For intrinsic region

$$J_n = q n(x) \mu_n E \left[\because q D_n \frac{dn}{dx} = 0 \right] \quad (11)$$

Differentiating equation (11)

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q(R_n - G_n) = -q G_n; [\because R_n = 0] \quad (12)$$

Solving equation (12)

$$n(x) = n(0) + \frac{f_0}{\mu_n E} [1 - e^{-\alpha D x}] \quad (13)$$

For the current density we have,

$$J_n(D) = q\mu_n E n(d) + qU_s^1 \quad (14)$$

$$\text{or, } J_n(0) = q\mu_n E n_d(0) + qU_s^1 \quad (15)$$

$$n_d(0) = \frac{1}{q\mu_n E} [J_n(0) - qU_s^1] \quad (16)$$

Combining equation (15) and (16)

$$n(0) = \frac{-B + \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{where, } A = \frac{q\mu_n E}{N_D \tau_C}$$

$$B = \left[q\mu_n E \left(\frac{n_1}{N_D \tau_C} + \frac{1}{\tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_{opt}} \right) - \frac{J_{n0}}{N_D \tau_C} + \frac{qN_s (1 - f_{n0})}{N_D \tau_C \tau_r} \right]$$

$$C = -J_{n0} \left(\frac{n_1}{N_D \tau_C} + \frac{1}{\tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_{opt}} \right) - \frac{qN_s n_1 (f_{n0} + \frac{1}{\tau_{opt}})}{N_D \tau_C}$$

$n(x)$ can be obtained using equation (13) and using equation(11), current density can also be obtained. Now taking the sum of the currents of all regions we get the total photo generated current. And considering the dark current the total current becomes

$$J = -J_{ph}(V_L) + J_0 \left(e^{\frac{V_L + J R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) \quad (18)$$

where J is total current, J_{ph} is photo generated current, J_0 is dark current, V_t is thermal voltage, V_{bi} is the bias voltage, W_i is the width of intrinsic layer. Equation (2) has been solved using analytical method.

Equation (6) suggests that if the width of intrinsic layer increases, the electric field decreases. As the electric field decreases photo generated current decreases. This causes the total current to fall.

The band gap of quantum dot has a huge impact on the open-circuit-voltage and short-circuit-current. If the band gap of quantum dot increases n_1 will also increase. This will increase the probability of QD stacks working as a generation center. So the open-circuit-voltage and short-circuit-current will increase.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section the simulated J-V characteristics is observed for the variation of N_s , W_i and E_{gd} . MATLAB is used for all the simulation purposes. The effect on J-V characteristics for changing the band gap of dot material, surface dot density and absorber layer width is also shown in this section.

As discussed in the theory, if N_s increases the short-circuit-current will increase. In Fig2 the simulated result shows similar effect.

Fig2 J-V Characteristics for different N_s

In theory, the effect of width of the intrinsic layer has been discussed. As mentioned before if the width of the intrinsic layer increases the total current will decrease. Fig3 shows this effect.

Fig 3 J-V characteristics for different w_i

As explained in the theory section with the increase of the QD band gap the open-circuit-voltage and short-circuit-current will increase. The simulation in Fig4 shows similar effect

Fig 4 J-V characteristics for different E_{gd}

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presents an analytical model of J-V characteristics for an InGaN-quantum-dot based solar cell that considers the effect of the series resistance and

the variation of load voltage for the first time in the literature. From the results and analysis shown in this work it can be said that a higher value of N_s is better as it produces more current. The width of the intrinsic layer should not be very high as it lowers the total current. And finally the value of the band gap of dot material should be not be low, because high band gap produces high open circuit voltage and short circuit current.

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